

CMIP DROP IN SESSIONS

Variables

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1 Introduction

The CMIP Panel and WGCM Infrastructure Panel (WIP) are committed to open and inclusive communication, engagement, and co-creation with the CMIP community and wider end users and stakeholders during the CMIP7 planning process. A first step was to establish several Task Teams to support the design, scope, and definition of the next phase of CMIP and evolution of CMIP infrastructure and future operationalisation. Further information on the CMIP Task Teams can be found [here](#).

Further, a series of regular drop-in sessions was launched in early 2023, facilitated by the CMIP International Project Office (CMIP IPO), to cover key aspects of CMIP7 design and development and promote community feedback to the CMIP governance and Task Teams.

This report provides a summary of the first CMIP Variables drop-in sessions held on 1 June 2023 and 8 June 2023 across two timeslots (16:00 UTC and 05:00 UTC respectively) to support equitable global participation.

These sessions aimed to facilitate community discussion on variable requirements as planning for CMIP7 gets underway. Each session was chaired by either CMIP Panel co-chair John Dunne (1st June) or CMIP Panel member Julie Arblaster (8th June) and led by one of the Data Request Task Team co-leads, Martin Juckes (CEDA/STFC, UK) or Chloe Mackallah (CSIRO, AU). During the sessions, attendees were asked to provide feedback on their evolving variable needs (in terms of complexity, volume, and timing) with respect to increasingly complex models. There were also discussions on meeting the demands of downstream users, and the capacity of models and workflows to support those needs.

Registration was open to anyone with an interest in CMIP variable requirements through the wcrp-cmip.org website. There were 77 registered participants (of which 46 attended) across the two online sessions from across the globe representing Model Intercomparison Projects (MIPs), modelling centre representatives, and infrastructure providers.

2 Context

The CMIP6 Data Request

The CMIP data request defines all the variables from a particular phase of CMIP simulations which should be saved and archived. As the complexity of CMIP phases has grown, so has the data request. The CMIP6 data request was the most extensive yet. It includes the variables for widespread use across many of the different CMIP6-endorsed model intercomparison projects (MIPs), and the more specialised requirements sometimes needed for only one MIP. The increase in requested data has placed new demands on the modelling centres producing data and the infrastructure requirements to provide storage and access to the CMIP6 data.

The new structure of CMIP6, with the DECK and historical simulations separated from CMIP6-endorsed MIP specific experiments led to new challenges in the data request, with the variable requirements changing over an extended period of time. In initial versions of the data requirements from different MIPs, the diagnostics were often not precisely defined. This led to several iterations and refinements being made before a final, well-defined version of the CMIP6 data request was reached. This created challenges for the modelling centres, who had to frequently re-run simulations to ensure the correct data was being archived. See Annex A for a summary of the CMIP6 data request creation process and some of its perceived issues.

The Data Request Task Team

Following review of the CMIP6 experience, it has been agreed that there needs to be more consistency of the request between related experiments, while allowing enough flexibility to avoid archiving redundant data. It has also been suggested that the model used for defining the priority of variables should be simplified: there should be more common template variable lists for experiments and a more cautious approach to applying top priority to data requirements.

The CMIP7 Data Request Task Team (TT) aims to ensure that a consolidated final request is ready when modelling centres need to start CMIP7 simulations. Their objectives are to:

1. Oversee the creation of the CMIP7 Data Request which should provide participating modelling centres with full details of CMIP7 output requirements from participating science teams.
2. Ensure that the CMIP7 output requirements accurately reflect both the ambition of the science teams, the constraints of the data managing services, and the resources of the modelling centres.

The TT is currently working on developing a strategic approach for the CMIP7 data request. This approach should maintain a similar structure to previous versions to minimise effort required for interpreting the request and making clearer links with external sources of information, such as the controlled vocabularies (CVs).

The team was selected during an open call process in late 2022 with members from MIPs, infrastructure providers and modelling centres. Full details on the task team can be found [here](#) and within the [session slide deck](#).

3 Session format and programme

The aim of the sessions was to gain an understanding attendees' aspirations for the CMIP7 data request, gather further insight from their CMIP6 experience, and any foreseen potential challenges on a realm-by-realm basis. The sessions were designed to provide participants with information and, importantly, allow for open feedback and discussion through online Slido polls, from oral questions, and using an online Padlet ideas board (see Annex B).

A high-level update on CMIP7 planning from John Dunne (1st June) and Julie Arblaster (8th June) opened the session before the Data Request Task Team co-leads, Martin Jukes and Chloe Mackallah, provided an overview of the CMIP7 Data Request Task Team and the intended objectives of the drop-in sessions. Event attendees were then encouraged to choose from a number of breakout rooms: Oceanography; Cryosphere; Atmosphere, cloud physics and aerosols; Land surface; Impacts, mitigation, and downscaling. In the breakout rooms, discussions were led by a chair where engagement through oral discussion and online Padlet contributions was strongly encouraged. Following feedback from the first session on 1st June, some of the breakout rooms were merged for the second session. Breakout room themes and their respective chairs can be found in the table below:

Breakout room theme	Breakout room chair (1 June)	Breakout room chair (8 June)
Oceanography	John Dunne	Chloe Mackallah
Cryosphere	Martin Jukes	<i>(Merged with oceanography)</i>
Atmosphere, cloud physics, and aerosols	Christopher Goddard	Julie Arblaster
Land surface	Charlotte Pascoe	<i>(Merged with atmosphere)</i>
Impacts, mitigation, and downscaling	Alexander Ruane	Claas Teichmann

The session slide deck is available [here](#) aligning with the session programme below:

Topic	Slides	Lead
Welcome, housekeeping, and introductory Slido polls	1-8	Eleanor O'Rourke
Presentation: Status of CMIP7 planning	9-18	John Dunne/Julie Arblaster
Feedback: CMIP7 variable requirements	19-21	Martin Jukes/Chloe Mackallah
Presentation: CMIP6 Data Request feedback and breakout session aims	22-27	Martin Jukes/Chloe Mackallah
Breakout rooms: Understanding aspirations, concerns, and reservations		Breakout discussion chairs
Breakout room summaries and key take homes	28-29	John Dunne/Julie Arblaster, Martin Jukes/Chloe Mackallah, and Breakout discussion chairs
Next steps	30-31	Eleanor O'Rourke

4 Breakout summaries

Participants in both sessions were welcome to participate in the breakout groups that aligned with their expertise and interest with the opportunity to attend more than one if they desired. Below the aspirations and challenges from each breakout group are summarised. Common themes across the all breakout groups are synthesised in the next section. Full written input can be found in the Padlet board (see Annex B).

Atmosphere, cloud physics and aerosols

Participants in the Atmosphere, cloud physics, and aerosols breakout sessions engaged in lively discussion. This session was chaired by Christopher Goddard (ECMWF) in the first session, and CMIP Panel member Julie Arblaster (Monash University) for the second session. A few themes were brought up consistently across the breakout sessions. These are summarised below, followed by a summary of the oral discussion within each breakout group.

The need for a smaller data request

Modelling centre representatives stressed the need to have a smaller and simpler data request for CMIP7. In particular, it was raised that the changes to the CMIP6 data request which happened after simulations had begun added a lot of additional work. Discussions also identified that it is important that any changes to the data request, whether adding or removing variables, should be strongly driven by scientific and/or climate services requirements.

Consistency of derived variables and improved documentation

The topic of documentation was raised multiple times. There was general consensus that documentation should be better in general. Specifically, it was also suggested that for CMIP7, derived variables should have a centrally defined derivation for consistency across modelling centres. Additionally, some attendees noted that we could learn from previous CMIP phases where computational and storage access was far lower when considering which variables need to be archived. We should look back at the downstream analysis which was done versus providing the variables directly. With better documentation, it would be easier for users to derive variables offline.

New opportunities for aerosol and biogeochemistry variables

Session participants representing MIPs highlighted that with each CMIP phase there is an increase in model complexity. Specifically, for CMIP7 we are expecting more models using dynamic aerosol and biogeochemistry schemes. This creates an opportunity to request more complex variables. Though attendees also noted that, as above, new variable requests should have a strong scientific justification supporting them.

Tensions between resolution, variable requirements, and simplicity

An overarching theme from the breakout sessions was an understanding from participants that there are tensions between simplicity requirements from modelling centres, and scientific requirements

from the community. In particular, with increased resolution and complexity, new scientific avenues are regularly being identified. The CMIP7 Data Request Task Team should consider how best to manage these tensions. It was generally agreed that clear communication, documentation, and a more static data request could ease some of the issues seen in CMIP6.

Cryosphere

During the first session, the cryosphere breakout discussions were chaired by CMIP7 Data Request Task Team co-lead Martin Jukes (STFC). In the second session on 8th June, the cryosphere breakout was merged with oceanography, and was chaired by Data Request Task Team co-lead Chloe Mackallah (CSIRO). During the first session, this breakout group was small, nevertheless some interesting points were raised that should be considered. The main discussion point is detailed below.

Will dynamic ice sheet models be ready in time?

A possible complexity increase in CMIP7 might be the inclusion of dynamic ice sheet models. However, there are concerns over the initialisation of such models and whether this can be done in time for CMIP7. If dynamic ice sheets are ready, this would change the variable requirements from the cryosphere community. However, this uncertainty could lead to issues in how early the data request can be defined.

Impacts, mitigation, and downscaling

There was a lot of engaging discussion in the breakout sessions addressing the requirements from the Impacts, Mitigation, and Downscaling communities. This group was chaired by VIACS Advisory Board members Alex Ruane (NASA GISS) in the first session and Claas Teichmann (GERICS) in the second session. The commonly raised ideas are detailed below.

Engagement and collaboration needed across communities could reduce the need for new CMIP7 data

Participants noted that it will be useful to increase engagement with boundary and intermediate organisations to ensure that they can access, interpret, and translate CMIP7 outputs into different applications. It was also highlighted that engaging with the bias-adjustment, downscaling, and emulator communities will enable users to get as much information out of the existing CMIP6 data as possible. This could reduce the amount of new data required from CMIP7. Although, the question of whether this simply shifts the burden from the data creators to the data users was raised.

Packages of variables

It was highlighted that there is a need to create ‘impacts-relevant’ packages of variables that allow for analysis of compound events and complex metrics. It would be particularly helpful if these packages are coupled with validation information and tools that allow for consistent aggregation. Packages could also help with the difficulty users sometimes face to find their needed variables. The packages could be arranged around data purpose or geographical region for example.

Land surface

The land surface breakout in session 1 was chaired by CMIP7 Data Request Task Team member Charlotte Pascoe (STFC). During the second session on 8th June, the Land breakout was merged with the Atmosphere breakout, and was chaired by CMIP Panel member Julie Arblaster (Monash University).

Increased complexity of land surface models

As with the atmospheric model components above, land surface models are becoming increasingly complex. Therefore, CMIP7 is likely to include more models with better representations of the land surface. This will lead to an increase in the variable requirements. In particular, variables to assess the hydrological cycle were highlighted as a necessity as this was poorly addressed in CMIP6.

Land variable consistency across models

Participants raised that, for multi-model comparisons, it is very important in CMIP7 that land variables are consistently available across models. A clear data request will make this easier for modelling centres to ensure. In particular, it was suggested that more variables available at a monthly resolution would be very useful.

Oceanography

In both sessions there was vibrant and engaged discussion among the participants. Session 1 was chaired by CMIP Panel Co-chair, John Dunne (NOAA/GFDL), and Session 2 was chaired by Data Request TT Co-lead, Chloe Mackallah (CSIRO). The following topics were identified as requiring, or benefitting, from effort as we move towards CMIP7:

Increased resolution and frequency ocean variables

There was seen to be a clear need to embrace higher resolution ocean models to represent ocean weather and eddies more fully. High frequency output to represent, for example, timing, intensity and duration of extremes more adequately, was also highly desired.

Improving engagement between MIPs and VIACS communities

Reflecting on CMIP6 experience there was seen to be a need for improved interaction between MIPs in the ocean realm to engage more deeply with the VIACS and downscaling communities to ensure their needs are well recognised by the modellers and clear dialogue can ensure a mutual understanding of capabilities and expectations. An example cited was that velocities were not saved by one modelling centre as unaware this was required by the downscaling community. The availability of the variables required to address and study marine heatwaves was also raised and is particularly topical this year.

Issues around regriding

Regridding was a main point of discussion as an issue requiring focus to identify the key challenge and priorities to address.

In CMIP6 there was an effort by some groups to develop tools to support standard regriding and data cleaning but were not completely successful. It was suggested this effort could be potentially standardised and wrapped into any developing CMIP data access tools. Some level of quality

checking was also suggested to exclude overlapping grids for example. There was previously consensus around regridding to 1 degree, but higher resolution models may require this to be revisited. Unstructured mesh models, and other increasingly complex grids, were seen to heighten the challenge further. However, the participants agree that with some modelling centres pushing resolution and others complexity do not want to be too prescriptive (e.g., not allowing native grids) and instead promote the development of community tools that are fluid and adaptable.

Availability of post-processed metrics, summary statistics or derived variables.

The potential need for post processed metrics, summary statistics or derived variables for users was raised with barotropic stream function identified as a good example as not suffering from the grid issue. The downstream calculation of summary statistics by end users may lead to download statistics for state variables being a poor reflection of interest in those variables themselves rather than the summary statistic. It was suggested that a list of recipes to easily derive variables out of ESGF-published variables and directly retrieve these derived variables via the ESGF could also considerably lower the data volume of the archive, and potentially number of variables.

5 Key findings and next steps

A number of aspirations and concerns were raised constantly across each breakout group and each drop-in session. It is crucial to address these thoughts to ensure the CMIP7 data request works for as many data providers, modelling centres, and downstream users as possible.

Increased model complexity will increase variable requirements

There are many new and improved developments which will hopefully be included in CMIP7 models. Across all of the different breakout groups, increases in model complexity were raised as something for the Data Request Task Team to consider when developing the next CMIP7 data request. There is a possibility that models could couple dynamic ice sheets, aerosols, land surface, and biogeochemistry to name a few. With these great increases in model complexity, there are justifications for an increase in the variables requested to allow the community to probe previously unattainable scientific questions. This increase in variables is at odds with the initial desire to reduce the requested variables from CMIP6, as the burden on modelling centres was too high. This should be carefully considered by the Data Request Task Team

The need for modelling centres to derive variables versus downstream derivation through clear documentation

Some suggestions were made on how to reduce the burden on modelling centres. One that came up across many of the different breakout groups was to what extent the modelling centres should be expected to archive derived variables from their simulations. It could help to reduce the burden on modelling centres to shift the derivation of variables onto the data users. However, this is not a simple solution as some participants raised the question of whether we should be shifting this burden onto data users. Particularly those with less computational power and storage would then have reduced ability to perform complex scientific studies.

Nevertheless, regardless of who derives variables, it was also made clear that better documentation should be provided on the calculation of derived variables to ensure consistency.

Good collaboration across different communities is essential

Participants across the event highlighted the need for better collaboration and engagement across different communities. This is needed to ensure that everyone has access to the data they need. Improved engagement could also lead to new post-processing and analysis techniques which could enable users to glean information more from the existing data. This would possibly reduce the amount of information requested from CMIP7, and thus reduce the data request as needed.

The Data Request Task Team thanks everyone for their input and engagement across these inaugural Variable Drop-In sessions. The points raised are invaluable and will be heavily considered when defining the data request process for CMIP7.

Moving forwards, the Task Team are currently developing a three-layer strategic approach to developing the CMIP7 Data Request and a thematic variable approach to extending the WCRP baseline variable list to form a request for the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC)

seventh assessment cycle timeline. The strategic approach is likely to include harmonised and unharmonised components. This will hopefully satisfy both the increased variable requirements from MIPs for answering expanded scientific questions, and the more controlled data request that allows for a set of experiments to align with the IPCC timeline. Keep track of the decision process for this strategic approach in the public [CMIP Decision Request Log](#).

And finally...please do keep in touch! The team welcomes all input - add your question to the [CMIP FAQ](#) question submission form or email cmip-ipo@esa.int.

6 Annex A – CMIP6 Data Request

The CMIP6 Data Request

The CMIP6 Data Request **defined all of the variables which should be output** from CMIP6 simulations. It consists of:

- An XML database with the data requirements for all MIPs,
- A browsable online version,
- A python library providing both a programmable and a command line interface.

What is it?

Why was it created?

CMIP6 was a global collaborative effort in which dozens of climate models ran a **coordinated set of experiments**. This created an extensive data archive to support **evaluation and intercomparison** of the climate models.

Data requirements were collected from the **23 CMIP6-endorsed MIPs**.

20 of the MIPs represented different scientific areas. Three MIPs represented the interests of communities which do not engage directly with the climate models:

- CORDEX requested data required to drive regional climate models
- ScenarioMIP did not make any data requests, but specified experiments to study climate change scenarios
- VIACS-AB compiled data requirements from climate change impacts and services experts

How was it created?

Perceived issues

The **scale and complexity** of the data request:

- The diversity of both those proposing requests and the facilities offering services led to a large, and highly complex data request.

Too many **high priority variables**:

- Discussion at WGCM 22 (Barcelona, 2019) highlighted around 50% of variables were designated as priority one (Juckes, 2020)

7 Annex B - Raw data

Idea submitted to the Padlet during the sessions can be read on the next page. Alternatively, the raw data can be downloaded as a CSV file from bit.ly/CMIP-Variables-dropin-data-June23. After following the link, click the ellipse and select Download CSV:

